

Artikov Eshpulat Ruziyevich

Associate Professor of the Department of
Music Performance and Culture
of Bukhara State University

Sharipov Akbar Anvarovich

Student of the Faculty of Arts,
Bukhara State University

Professional folk music created by musicians and singers over the centuries shows that the musical culture of the Uzbek people has a centuries-old history. The national music works of the ancestors of the Uzbek people are strongly connected with the creativity of the brotherly peoples who lived in the territory of Central Asia, first of all, the Tajik people¹.

The historical development in the cultural life of the peoples of Central Asia begins approximately in the first millennium before our era. The Central Asian peoples and their activities and lives are described in detail in the book "Avesta", a monument of the eastern countries² In the book of Avesta, the commonality of folk poetic and musical art and the musical and poetic works created on this basis, the life of the peoples of Central Asia, their politics, their customs, weddings, etc., are shown in archaeological samples. z is reflected. Peasants settling down, forming a family, a community and transitioning to a class society, the results of the gradual unification of states, the appearance of epic songs, and mural patterns are evidence of this. The valiant struggle of the peoples of Central Asia for freedom, the bravery of Cholpon Shiroq, who sacrificed his life on this path, has been reflected in history. Also, Ferdowsi's "Shahnama", an invaluable work of the peoples of the East, including the characters of the settled farmers (Sugdians, Bactrians, Khorezmiyars) and nomads (Saks, Massagets) in Central Asia from the first millennium AD. historical sources provide information. Legends were created about the bravery of Rustam, Sukhrob, Siovush, the love of the beauty queen, the symbol of beauty, and other heroes.

In the book "Avesta", which is considered as a historical source, it is shown that people sing and perform songs as a group in various ceremonies, people worship fire, sing and dance around it. Thus, according to the thinkers of the 12th-15th centuries, various traditions, singing,

¹ History of Uzbek music. Tashkent, 198L 5-p.

² Historical sources provide information about settled farmers (Sugdians, Bactrians, Khorezmiyars) and settlers (Sakas, Massagets) in Central Asia from the first millennium AD.

dancing, and the attitude of the people to music are clearly shown on the main holiday of the people, Navroz³. The attitude of ordinary people to music, later development of music, scientific and theoretical research found its place in the following works over the centuries: "Treatise about Music" - Muhammad Nishapuri, "Risolutush-Sharafiya" - Safiuddin Urtnavi, "Durat-ut taj-li ghurra yat-Diboj" - Qutbiddin Sherozi, "Nafois-ul-funun", "Li-arois-ulyunon" - Mahmoud Omuli, "Maholid-ul-ulum" - Mirsaid Alin Jurjani, "Maqasid-ul-alkhan" - Abdulkadir Maroghi, "Treatise about music" A. Jami, "Kitab-ul musiqa ul-kabir" al- Farobi, "Donishnama" Ibn Sina, "Treatise on Music" Kamaluddin Binai, "Scientific and practical law of music", Mahmud

Hosseini, "Treats on Music" by Najmuddin Kavkabi, Darvesh Ali Changi and others are among them. The presence of many features in ancient Central Asia is shown. This information is reflected in wall patterns and various sculptures. Political changes took place among the peoples of the East from the 4th century AD. Slavery was gradually replaced by the feudal system.

Eastern countries were divided into two groups and the process of living together with the Turkish and Eastern Iranian peoples began. The types of banquets and ceremonies, hunting scene on a silver tray, statue of a dancer shown in bright patterns found in the ancient city of Panjakent indicate that the culture of music was highly valued among the peoples of ancient Central Asia⁴. The musical heritage of local Turks is described in the "Book of Korqut"⁵. This book inspired the development of heroic epics created by different peoples. In connection with the adoption of Islam among the peoples of Central Asia in the 8th-9th centuries, local peoples began to live with this religious belief. Especially during this period, under the leadership of Muqanna, who represented the interests of the working classes among the people, the "White-clothed" movement took the main place in history. From this period, the era of Arab rule began in Central Asia.

The usika art of the local population and the Arab people merged, more local musicians learned Arabic music, and thus new works were created. When we turn to A. Mahony's "Book of Songs", we get the following information: that is, the first Arab singer, Musadjik, was in Central Asia, and he chose different tunes and based them on the system of performing songs created.

³ A Yritom Frieze - a fragment of the wall found in the city of Termiz during the archaeological expedition of M. Massoi to the Ayritom fortress proves this.

⁴ «O'zbek musiqa tarixi». Toshkent. 1981. 8-b.

⁵ Kitobi Dada Qo'rqut — turkiy xalqlarning XII-XV asrlarda yaratilgan qahramonlik qo'shiqlari. Ushbu ma'lumot «O'zbek musiqasi tarixi» kitobida ko'rsatilgan. 8-b.

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